

MODERN NEWSPAPER: TRANSFER OF MEANING

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Abstract. *In the article, the modern newspaper evaluates not only the metaphor and its impact on the reader, but also journalistic texts in terms of their topic and semantic organization, as well as the associative-evaluative type of persuasion carried out in socio-political and economic texts. important tool in the reflection of reality in the texts related to culture and science was analyzed.*

Keywords: *modern newspaper, journalistic style, metaphor, metonymy, concept.*

In linguistics, the problems of media language learning are relevant. Today, in world linguistics, in particular, in Karakalpak and Uzbek linguistics, scientific research based on establishing the lexical-stylistic and structural compositional features of the material published in the periodical press is both a necessary and a complex task.

The modern newspaper metaphor is a characteristic feature of the author's individual style in covering the speech situation, which is based on the reflection of reality and journalistic approach. Therefore, as one of the methods of creating meaning, metaphor is the use of a word that denotes a certain class of objects, events, actions, or characteristics that are used to describe or define another class of objects or persons (similar and dissimilar). Indeed, a metaphor is "a tool that not only appears in the mind of a person in the process of mental activity, but also creates understanding, parallelism, similarities, and also has a modality, evaluative and emotional image of the surrounding world. Thus, the metaphor becomes a tool for studying the realities of reality, when the conceptual content corresponding to the level of thinking, mental analogies of objects work.

It should be noted that metaphor in the artistic style is considered as a stylistic tool or an artistic tool, both as a process of creating a new meaning in the process of rethinking language expressions, and as a ready-made metaphorical meaning. In the journalistic style, metaphor - as a means of nomination, even in rare cases - a method of cognitive manipulation of the meanings available in the language in order to see new things, is considered an important tool in the accurate reflection of the linguistic image of the world, especially the direct reality.

In fact, as subjects that create the basis of a metaphor, a plant, a goal, a foundation, an emerging idea about the world (object, event, property, event, fact) and an auxiliary concept - about the world that has already manifested itself in the language in the form of the "literal meaning" of any phrase it is also a means of illuminating an idea. For example, V.V. Yunev distinguishes the following stages of metaphor creation:

- 1) heterogeneous, assuming similarity of individuals;
- 2) focusing, containing tools that create context to actualize specific features and associations;
- 3) filtering, that is, the combination of directed features and associations of the new concept and "direct meaning".

At the same time, the scientist's opinion about the "Idea of Metaphor" is very appropriate, in which "metaphor, despite the fact that the subject creates a new meaning through nomination

and is a suitable tool for its expression, becomes a new concept through the process of naming and plays the role of a function." metaphor is a phenomenon based on the similarity between two essences, that is, it consists in finding their common features. It is a mental and linguistic mechanism that involves the interaction of events or their comparison. Since ancient times, the role of metaphor in cognition has been to compare different essences and establish connections.

F.I. Abdulkhairova distinguishes the following features of metaphor:

1) metaphor is an integral part of scientific method and terminological system of science;

2) it acts as a tool for enriching scientific language (emergence of new terms, etc.);

3) almost all types of metaphors and metaphorical transfers are presented in scientific method texts;

4) evaluative-expressive metaphors are almost absent in scientific texts;

5) figurative metaphors are used to make scientific information more accessible and easy to understand;

6) metaphor serves as a vector for further development of scientific knowledge.

As a phenomenon of metonymy in linguistics: a) a means of creating artistic speech as tropes; b) as a method of semantic changes of word meaning; c) as a means of nomination; d) as a means of conceptualizing and organizing knowledge.

N.D. Arutyunova, metaphor and metonymy are positionally syntagmatic relations. Metaphor and metonymy are thought to have different functional roles. Metaphor gives importance to the object, and metonymy identifies and actualizes the object it will have an individualizing feature.

As for metonymic transfer, polysemy is a category that reflects both the universal characteristics of language and thought, and the national language characteristics, and the ambiguity of the form is the objective law of language existence. The reason for this can be seen in the fact that the human memory cannot remember and store language tools that reflect a large number of concepts.

The problem of metonymy, like metaphor in linguistics, is always related to their two functions. It was noted above that artistic speech and the phenomenon of nomination are among them. In fact, the nominative function of metonymy, metonymic and metaphorical transfers began to be considered not only as a method of the historical development of the language, but also as a means of organizing a synchronic system of the dictionary.

The interrelationship of the meanings contained in the polyseme lexeme takes place on the basis of metonymy and synecdoche. Transferring the name of one subject to another subject based on mutual relation is called metonymy.

– some of the patterns of inter-meaning connection based on metonymy in the Uzbek language are as follows:

– subject and another subject in the same subject: head (the upper part of the human body above the neck) - head (brain, headache);

– subject and the subject formed from this subject: tea (type of plant) - tea (drink made from the leaves of this plant), coffee (type of plant) - coffee (drink made from the fruit of this plant), language (nutkazosi) - language (nugq);

– a symbol and an object with this symbol: blue (color) - blue (green), dirt ("dirty") - laundry (dirty or washed clothes);

– object and unit of measurement based on this object: day (sun) - day (light part of the day), moon (celestial body) - moon (twelfth of a year).

The recognition of metonymy as one of the types of connection between polysemantic word meanings allows to dwell on the linguistic conditions (semantic and grammatical) that help or limit the development of metonymic constructions.

Since the phenomenon of meaning transfer is one of the most powerful tools of persuasion important to journalism, researchers have identified two types of indirect persuasion in journalistic texts.

Distinguish the main types: associative-evaluative and emotional-aesthetic.

It is understood that each method of persuasion is shaped by different movements and used in different texts. The associative-evaluative type of persuasion is characterized by evaluative metaphors, metonymy, synecdoche, and tasking, which are implemented in socio-political and economic texts, for the emotional-aesthetic type, for example, artistic metaphors, which are implemented in cultural and scientific texts. It is important to consider not only the metaphor and its impact on the reader, but also journalistic texts from the point of view of their topic and semantic organization.

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